

DIALOGUE ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

	Overall proficiency (spoken interaction)	Range	Accuracy	Fluency	Pronunciation	Interaction
A1	Can interact in a simple way if the interlocutor repeats at a slower rate and rephrases their message and language if needed. Can produce simple questions and react to similar language.	Has a very basic repertoire of words and separate phrases related to personal details and particular concrete situations.	Shows only limited control of a few simple grammatical structures and sentence patterns in a memorized repertoire.	Can manage very short, isolated, mainly pre-packaged utterances. Often pauses to search for expressions, to articulate less familiar words pronunciation and to repair communication.	Pronunciation of a very limited repertoire of learnt words and phrases can be understood with some effort by interlocutors used to dealing with speakers of the language group concerned. Can reproduce correctly a limited range of sounds as well as stress on simple, familiar words and phrases.	Can ask and answer questions about personal details. Can interact in a simple way but communication is totally dependent on repetition, rephrasing and repair.
A2	Can interact with reasonable ease in structured situations and short conversations, provided the other person helps if necessary. Can ask and answer questions and exchange ideas and information on familiar topics in predictable everyday situations.	Can use short, memorized phrases, groups of a few words and basic sentence patterns. Can use them to communicate limited information in simple everyday situations.	Uses some simple structures correctly, but still systematically makes basic mistakes.	Can make themselves understood in very short utterances, even though pauses, false starts and reformulation are very evident.	Pronunciation is generally clear enough to be understood, but conversational partners will need to ask for repetition from time to time. A strong influence from the other language(s) they speak on stress, rhythm and intonation may affect intelligibility, requiring collaboration from interlocutors. Nevertheless, pronunciation of familiar words is clear.	Can ask and answer questions and respond to simple statements. Can indicate when they are following but is rarely able to understand enough to keep conversation going of their own accord.
DIFFERENCES A2 > B1: Can participate in longer discussions, can manage conversation without support from the interlocutor, can produce more speech, not just short and simple sentences.						
B1	Can enter unprepared into conversation on familiar every-day topics and express personal opinions. Can exchange, check and confirm information. Can explain why something is a problem.	Has enough language to get by in every-day practical situations. Has sufficient vocabulary to express themselves on familiar topics such as family, hobbies and interests, work, travel and current events. Expresses themselves with some hesitation and occasionally resorts to circumlocution.	Uses reasonably accurately a repertoire of frequently used expressions and grammatical patterns associated with easily predictable situations.	Can produce continuous and comprehensive speech. Pausing due to grammatical and lexical planning and repair is common, especially in longer stretches of free production.	Pronunciation is generally intelligible. Can approximate intonation and stress at both utterance and word levels. However, accent is usually influenced by the other language(s) they speak.	Can initiate, maintain and close simple face-to-face conversation on topics that are familiar or of personal interest. Can repeat part of what someone has said to confirm mutual understanding.
B2	Can use language quite fluently, accurately and effectively and clearly mark the relationships between ideas. Can communicate nearly spontaneously with quite good grammatical control. There are some shortcomings in language skills, which restrict what can be expressed.	Has a sufficient range of language to give clear descriptions and express viewpoints on most general topics, without much conspicuous searching for words. Uses some complex sentence forms.	Shows a relatively high degree of grammatical control. Does not make errors that cause misunderstanding, and can correct most of their mistakes.	Can produce continuous speech quite fluently, although can be hesitant in searching for suitable patterns and expressions. There are few noticeably long pauses.	Can generally use appropriate intonation, place stress correctly and articulate individual sounds clearly. Accent tends to be influenced by the other language(s) they speak but has little or no effect on intelligibility.	Can initiate discourse, take their turn when appropriate and end conversation when they need to, though they may not always do this elegantly. Can help the discussion along on familiar ground confirming comprehension or inviting others in the conversation.
DIFFERENCES B2 > C1: Language use is very effortless and it does not restrict what they can express, can discuss more complex topics, can discuss topics with greater variety and depth.						
C1	Can express themselves fluently, spontaneously and effortlessly. Has a such good command of a broad lexical repertoire that gaps can be readily overcome with circumlocutions. There is little obvious searching for expressions or avoidance strategies.	Has a good command of a broad range of language resources. Can select a formulation to express themselves clearly in an appropriate style without having to restrict what they want to say. Can discuss a wide variety of topics related to, for example, general matters, studies and research, professional issues or leisure activities.	Consistently maintains a high degree of grammatical accuracy. Errors are rare, difficult to spot and are generally corrected when they do occur.	Can express themselves fluently and spontaneously, almost effortlessly. Only a conceptually difficult subject can cause linguistic hesitations.	Can employ the full range of phonological features in the target language with sufficient control to ensure intelligibility throughout. Can articulate virtually all the sounds of the target language. Some features of accent retained from other language(s) may be noticeable, but they do not affect intelligibility at all.	Can select a suitable phrase from a readily available range of discourse functions to preface their remarks in order to get or to keep the floor and to relate their own contributions skillfully to those of other speakers.
C2	Has a good command of idiomatic expressions and colloquialisms with awareness of connotative levels of meaning. Can convey finer shades of meaning precisely. Can backtrack and restructure around a difficulty so smoothly that the interlocutor is hardly aware of it.	Shows great flexibility reformulating ideas in differing linguistic forms to convey finer shades of meaning precisely, to give emphasis and to eliminate ambiguity. Can use language-specific idiomatic expressions and colloquialisms correctly and appropriately.	Maintains consistent grammatical control of complex language, even while attention is otherwise engaged (e.g. in forward planning or in monitoring others' reactions).	Can express themselves spontaneously with quite long and natural colloquial expressions, avoiding or backtracking around any difficulty so smoothly that the interlocutor is hardly aware of it.	Can employ the full range of phonological features in the target language with a high level of control – including prosodic features such as word and sentence stress, rhythm and intonation – so that the finer points of their message are clear and precise. Intelligibility is not affected in any way by features of accent that may be retained from other language(s).	Can interact with ease and skill, picking up and using non-verbal and intonational cues apparently effortlessly. Can interweave their contribution into the joint discourse with fully natural turn taking and referencing, for example.

Sources: (1) Council of Europe (2020). *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, teaching, assessment – Companion volume*. Council of Europe Publishing. www.coe.int/lang-cefr. (2) Huttunen, I., & Jaakkola, H. (2003).

Eurooppalainen viitekehys: Kielten oppimisen, opettamisen ja arvioinnin yhteinen eurooppalainen viitekehys (Finnish translation). WSOY.

Edits to the original Finnish version: Coherence column deleted. Added "Pronunciation". "Error-free" changed to "Accuracy". Pronunciation translated to match with CEFR 2020. Range, Accuracy, Fluency and Interaction edited to match CEFR 2020 (pp. 183-5). Overall proficiency (CEFR, 2020, p. 72) partly shortened as in "Overall oral interaction", based on the Finnish translation (Huttunen & Jaakkola, 2003, p. 112, section "Suullinen vuorovaikutus"). The differences between A-, B and C-levels added.

Translation to English done for publication purposes.